

Recruiting for Parkinson's disease risk: Successful engagement tactics to screen for hyposmia in undiagnosed individuals

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1 INTRODUCTION

Early clinical markers of PD are critical to identify biomarker signatures before typical PD symptoms occur. Studies including the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) have identified smell loss (hyposmia) as a screening tool for disease risk. In mid-2022, PPMI launched the Smell Test Direct system to remotely screen for smell loss in individuals **aged 60 and older without PD**. Participants consent and enter contact information online, are mailed a 40-question scratch-and-sniff smell test (the University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test or UPSIT) and enter answers in a web-based portal. PPMI invites select individuals for additional screening at a one of 30+ clinical sites; some will be invited to enroll for longitudinal assessment.

2 METHODS

To engage a broad population of people without a Parkinson's diagnosis, PPMI and sponsor The Michael J. Fox Foundation (MJFF) have engaged in a multi-faceted recruitment approach. Recruitment is ongoing in the U.S., Canada and England and will begin soon in the Netherlands.

Recruitment Efforts

Paid Online & TV Ads <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Display ads & social ads Search promotion TV commercial 		
Owned Content <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog posts & web pages Emails & social posts 		

3 RESULTS

Smell Test Direct has seen over 290,000 unique website visitors, 33,000+ consented and 2,300+ hyposmics identified.

Smell Test Direct Funnel Performance

Campaign Performance in Driving Consents & Identifying Hyposmics

Campaign Type	Total Consents	Total Hyposmics Identified
Ambassadors	1,115 (3.3%)	77 (3.2%)
Earned Media	223 (0.6%)	30 (1.3%)
MJFF Owned Content	8,391 (24.6%)	552 (23.2%)
Paid Online & TV Ads	17,353 (50.8%)	1,153 (48.5%)
Paid Newspaper Ads	494 (1.4%)	39 (1.6%)
Paid Referral Partnerships	2,056 (6%)	139 (5.8%)
Senior Living Community Outreach	980 (2.9%)	80 (3.4%)
Senior Living Direct Mail	378 (1.1%)	30 (1.3%)
Site Outreach	228 (0.7%)	23 (1%)
Unknown Campaign	2,933 (8.6%)	256 (10.7%)

4 DISCUSSION

Our approach utilized varied efforts over the first 12 months of the program. With learnings around return on investment (ROI) for general recruitment, we are now finetuning our approach to maximize ROI and testing efforts toward engaging historically underrepresented populations.

Paid media and advertisements have yielded significant return, as has tapping existing enriched audiences such as community members engaging with The Michael J. Fox Foundation or individuals who have opted to hear of research opportunities from companies and organizations (Quest Diagnostics, Smell and Taste Association of North America). While senior living outreach did engage study volunteers, we found the approach required greater investment of personnel resources. A centralized, remote screening core de-emphasized the need for outreach by each site team (with study sponsor playing a more active role) and made it easier for individual and community organization partners to refer participants.

5 CONCLUSION

A multi-faceted approach has successfully engaged undiagnosed individuals in hyposmia testing. These findings could be utilized for brain health studies enrolling this population.

6 REFERENCES

PPMI, a public-private partnership, is funded by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research and funding partners, including 4D Pharma, Abbvie, AcureX, Allergan, Amathus Therapeutics, Aligning Science Across Parkinson's, AskBio, Avid Radiopharmaceuticals, BIAL, Biogen, Biohaven, BioLegend, BlueRock Therapeutics, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Calico Labs, Celgene, Cerevel Therapeutics, Coave Therapeutics, DaCapo Brainscience, Denali, Edmond J. Safra Foundation, Eli Lilly, GE HealthCare, Genentech, GSK, Golub Capital, Gain Therapeutics, Handl Therapeutics, Insitro, Janssen Neuroscience, Lundbeck, Merck, Meso Scale Discovery, Mission Therapeutics, Neurocrine Biosciences, Pfizer, Piramal, Prevail Therapeutics, Roche, Sanofi, Servier, Sun Pharma Advanced Research Company, Takeda, Teva, UCB, Vanqua Bio, Verily, Voyager Therapeutics, the Weston Family Foundation and Yumanity Therapeutics